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Hypogonadotropic Hypogonadism in a Patient with Morbid Obesity

Mollar-Puchades MA¹, Cámara-Gómez R¹, del Olmo García MI¹, Ponce-Marco JL²,
Segovia-Portolés R¹, Abellán-Galiana P¹, Piñón-Sellés F¹.

¹Unit of Endocrinology, Universitary Hospital La Fe, Valencia, Spain.

²Unit of Endocrine Surgery, Universitary Hospital La Fe, Valencia, Spain.

Authors: Miguel Angel Mollar Puchades, M.D.; Rosa Cámara Gómez, M.D., Maria Isabel del Olmo García, M.D.; José Luis Ponce Marco, M.D.; Raquel Segovia Portolés, M.D.; Pablo Abellán Galiana, M.D.; Francisco Piñón Sellés, Ph.D.

Correspondence: Miguel Angel Mollar Puchades. Universitary Hospital La Fe, Av Campanar, 21. 46009 Valencia, Spain. Tel. 0034961973165. e-mail: mimopu@comv.es

Running title: Obesity and hypogonadotropic hypogonadism.

Abstract

Obesity has recently become one of the most important public health problems. It is associated with a high rate of mortality, mainly because of cardiovascular disease, and can cause hormonal abnormalities such as hypogonadotropic hypogonadism. Weight loss is very beneficial for obese patients, as it results in improvement or even normalization of these conditions. In this report, we describe a morbidly obese patient with hypogonadotropic hypogonadism, which was probably caused by hyperprolactinemia and exacerbated by obesity-induced hormonal imbalances. After medical treatment for hyperprolactinemia and bariatric surgery, the patient's hormonal status became normal. Although morbid obesity can cause hypogonadotropic hypogonadism in men, the differential diagnosis should include other potential causes of hypogonadism if free testosterone levels are below normal.

Key words: Hypogonadotropic hypogonadism, morbid obesity, hyperprolactinemia, bariatric surgery, hyperestrogenism, weight loss, pituitary adenoma

Introduction

During recent years, obesity has become one of the most important public health problems. It is considered a chronic disease characterized by an increase in body fat and body weight. It is associated with a high rate of mortality, which is mainly caused by cardiovascular disease. Obesity can also result in hormonal imbalances. Weight loss is very beneficial for obese patients, as it improves or even normalizes this condition.¹

Morbid obesity affects various hormones. It decreases basal plasma levels of growth hormone and the response of growth hormone to stimuli such as arginine- and insulin-induced hypoglycemia.² It increases serum cortisol concentrations but circadian rhythm is not impaired; however, elevated cortisol levels can be suppressed by dexamethasone administration. Low plasma triiodothyronine (T3) levels may occur in obese people, but this has no clinical relevance.³ The relationship between obesity, insulin resistance, and hyperinsulinism has been the subject of numerous publications.⁴

In obese women, common findings include hyperandrogenism of ovarian origin,⁵ chronic anovulation accompanied by elevated plasma luteinizing hormone (LH) levels and ratios between LH and follicle stimulating hormone (FSH). In men, obesity can cause hypogonadotropic hypogonadism,⁶ oligospermia, impotence, impaired libido, and low plasma levels of total testosterone (TT).⁷ However, these effects are usually not clinically relevant, as serum levels of gonadotropin and free testosterone (FT), the active form of testosterone, are normal. Plasma FT levels are only low in cases of extreme obesity.⁸ This report describes a morbidly obese patient with hypogonadotropic hypogonadism, which was probably caused by hyperprolactinemia and exacerbated by a hormonal imbalance caused by obesity.

Case report

A 39-year-old man without a relevant clinical history or a history of toxic abuse was referred to us for assessment of the suitability of bariatric surgery for treatment of his extreme morbid obesity. The patient reported that his weight had increased progressively since he was 19 years old despite many low-calorie diets. In the directed anamnesis, he did not exhibit any symptoms of endocrine imbalances. At the first physical examination, his weight was 184 kg and his body mass index (BMI) was 64.4 kg/m². He was slightly pale, had slight skin atrophy, and did not display regression of secondary sexual characters. The rest of the physical examination was normal.

The results of blood testing were: total cholesterol, 229 mg/dl (normal = 50–235 mg/dl); high-density lipoprotein cholesterol, 42 mg/dl (normal = 35–99 mg/dl); low-density lipoprotein cholesterol, 166 mg/dl (normal = 0–150 mg/dl); hemoglobin, 14.4 g/dl (normal = 14–18 g/dl); immunoreactive leptin, 98.40 ng/ml (normal for obese people = 31.3 ± 24 ng/dl), FSH, 1.2 mIU/l (normal = 2–10 mIU/l); LH, 1.8 mIU/l (normal = 1.5–10 mIU/l); estradiol, 50 pg/ml (normal = 11–45 pg/ml); TT, 0.75 ng/ml (normal = 3–10 ng/ml); FT, 2.98 pg/ml (normal = 8.8–27 pg/ml); sex hormone binding globulin (SHBG), 13 nM/l (normal = 10–40 nM/l); dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate, 1709 ng/ml (normal = 2000–4000 ng/ml); insulin levels before and 60 min after an oral glucose tolerance test of 18.5 μ IU/ml (normal = 5–25 μ IU/ml) and 114 μ IU/ml, respectively; and normal glucose levels. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) could not be performed because the patient's girth was too great to fit into the MRI chamber. The patient was given a diet that supplied 1500 kcal per day and hypophyseal assessment was repeated (Table 1). After hypophyseal stimulation with an intravenous bolus of 100 μ g gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH), the increase in FSH and LH levels was

normal (the increase in LH level was greater than that of FSH), and the basal TT and FT levels were 0.91 ng/ml and 1.65 pg/ml respectively. The diagnosis of secondary hypogonadotropic hypogonadism was confirmed. Hyperprolactinemia was detected (prolactin, 82.6 ng/ml; normal = 0.5–20 ng/ml).

MRI was performed when the patient's weight had decreased to 156 kg. An intrasellar **pituitary** tumor with depression and possible rupture of the sellar surface was detected. The tumor was 1 cm in diameter and showed low uptake after contrast administration; the stalk was not displaced (Figure 1). Treatment with cabergoline (0.5 mg per week) was commenced, and the patient exhibited good tolerance. Blood tests were repeated 3 months later, at which time the patient's weight was 149 kg. The results were: FSH, 2.8 mIU/ml; LH, 3.9 mIU/ml; estradiol, 40 pg/ml; TT, 2.68 ng/ml; FT, 6.2 pg/ml; and prolactin, 11.6 ng/ml. MRI performed 6 months after commencement of treatment with cabergoline revealed that the diameter of the adenoma had decreased to 7 mm (Figure 2). The patient reported an improvement in libido and sexual potency.

When the patient weighed 140 kg and was asymptomatic, bariatric surgery consisting of vertical banded gastroplasty and gastro-jejunal bypass was performed. There were no complications during or after surgery. Six months after surgery, the patient remained asymptomatic, his weight was 104 kg, and the results of blood testing were: FSH, 3.6 mIU/ml; LH, 4.9 mIU/ml; estradiol, 26 mIU/ml; TT, 5.63 ng/ml; FT, 14.2 pg/ml; SHBG, 36 nM/l; prolactin, 14.2 ng/ml (the patient was still receiving cabergoline); and insulin, 5.11 μ IU/ml. Another hypophyseal stimulation test with an intravenous bolus of 100 μ g GnRH yielded the following results: the basal FSH level of 3.7 mIU/ml increased to 8.3 mIU/ml after 60 minutes and the basal LH level of 6.0 mIU/ml increased to 43,1 mIU/ml after 60 minutes. **The patient is currently asymptomatic,**

with normal prolactin levels, and without mass effects. Considering the good evolution and by common consent with the patient it has been decided to continue monitoring with pituitary MRI and visual field assessment.

Discussion

Hypogonadotropic hypogonadism is characterized by low plasma testosterone levels and normal or low gonadotropin (FSH and LH) concentrations, as was the case with our patient. Hypogonadotropic hypogonadism can be caused by any disease that affects the hypothalamic–hypophyseal axis in the following ways: decreased GnRH synthesis or release, interference with the passage of GnRH through the hypophyseal axis because of compression or damage, or decreased FSH and LH release caused by direct hypophyseal damage.

Hyperprolactinemia causes hypogonadotropic hypogonadism in men, which results in low libido, impotence, and low fertility. As in women, the severity of symptoms is usually related to the degree of hyperprolactinemia. In our patient, prolactin levels were only slightly elevated, which explains the lack of symptoms. In addition, patients with extreme morbid obesity do not usually complain of low libido and impotence unless they are asked about their sexual performance, because they consider these conditions normal for people with excessive weight.

Hypophyseal macroadenomas cause hyperprolactinemia either by direct release of prolactin (prolactinoma) or by inhibiting hypophyseal release of hypothalamic inhibitory hormones because of their mass. Plasma prolactin concentration usually correlates with the size of the adenoma. Prolactin releasing microadenomas (microprolactinomas) tend to result in prolactin levels less than 200 ng/dl; those with diameters of 1–2 cm result in prolactin levels of 200–1000 ng/dl; and those with

diameters greater than 2 cm result in prolactin levels of more than 2000 ng/dl. However, some patients with large macroadenomas only exhibit slight hyperprolactinemia. In general, these adenomas are less differentiated than other prolactinomas and respond less to dopaminergic agonist drugs. In our patient, prolactin levels were initially not as high as would be expected of a macroprolactinoma and the response to the treatment with cabergoline was very good. This would support a diagnosis of nonfunctioning macroadenoma with hyperprolactinemia caused by interference with the release of inhibitory peptides. **Nonfunctioning pituitary adenomas are slow-growing benign tumors. The vast majority (>80%) of clinically non-functioning pituitary adenomas are gonadotroph-cell adenomas, as demonstrated by immunocytochemistry. Patients generally present with signs and symptoms relating to local mass effect, although because of the increased availability and use of MRI, an increasing numbers of patients also present with incidentally diagnosed pituitary adenomas. They require treatment if they are macroadenomas (over 1 cm in diameter), or produce symptoms due to impairment of hormone release or to compression of adjacent structures. The treatment of choice is surgical with post surgical radiotherapy if necessary, although some studies support that medical treatment with dopamin agonists or somatostatin analogues could also be effective. In our patient the treatment with cabergoline was commenced because of the hyperprolactinemia and because the assessment could not be completed until the patient lost weight.**^{9,10}

There are several mechanisms by which obesity causes hypogonadotropic hypogonadism in men. Firstly, a decrease in the serum SHBG levels and a consequent decrease in plasma TT levels may be responsible. Hyperinsulinemia is considered to

decrease SHBG levels.¹¹ Our patient initially had hyperinsulinemia and SHBG levels corresponding to the lower normal limit, but his SHBG levels increased as his BMI and insulinemia decreased. Low SHBG levels could result in low TT levels, but not in low FT levels, which were also present. Low FT levels have been associated with failure of the gonadal feedback regulatory system.¹²

Hypogonadotropic hypogonadism can also be caused by elevated plasma estrogen levels,¹³ which are caused by conversion in adipose tissue of testosterone to estrogen by an aromatase that is induced by gonadotropins. In our patient, serum estradiol levels were high initially, but decreased as the patient lost weight, especially after bariatric surgery, and eventually reached normal levels. The initial gonadotropin suppression in our patient probably attenuated the increase in plasma estrogen levels. Prolactin release increases in proportion to serum estrogen concentration, possibly because estrogen binds to hypophyseal lactotroph cells. Some authors have related high estrogen levels to hypophyseal adenomas and the growth of prolactinomas.¹⁴

It has also been suggested that hypogonadotropic hypogonadism of obese men could be caused by a decrease in plasma FSH concentration, a lower frequency of LH pulses caused by high estrogen levels, or to a decrease in GnRH pulse frequency and amplitude.¹² In our patient, FSH levels were initially suppressed and LH levels, although within the normal range, were inappropriately low considering that FT levels were low. This implies that the function of the hypothalamus–hypophysis axis was impaired, which is in concordance with other reports of the endocrinology of morbidly obese people.¹⁵ After stimulation with a single GnRH bolus, the LH level increased considerably, reflecting the low testosterone levels¹⁶ and the ability of hypophyseal cells to accumulate LH.

Leptin has an inhibitory effect on steroidogenesis in Leydig cells.¹⁷ In patients who have undergone bariatric surgery, zinc deficiency may cause hypogonadism by decreasing testicular production of testosterone.¹⁸

Various treatments for hypogonadotropic hypogonadism in obese patients have been proposed, the best of which is weight loss. This decreases or even normalizes hormonal imbalances and improves quality of life by improving sexual performance.¹⁹ Treatment with aromatase inhibitors has a similar effect to that of weight loss because it decreases estrogen levels.²⁰

In our patient, treatment with cabergoline normalized hyperprolactinemia and decreased the size of the tumor. Although the hyperprolactinemia played a fundamental role in the development of the patient's hypogonadism, weight loss, which increased SHBG plasma levels and decreased insulin and estrogen levels, contributed to the normalization of the function of the hypothalamic–hypophyseal axis and the regression of hypogonadism. The decrease in plasma estrogen levels was also important, because it eliminates stimuli that promote growth of prolactinomas.

Conclusion

Morbid obesity can cause hypogonadotropic hypogonadism in men. However, other potential causes of hormonal imbalances should be ruled out before they can be ascribed to obesity, particularly if FT levels are low. Weight loss is beneficial for obesity-related hypogonadism, and facilitates easier assessment and follow-up of other potential causes of hypogonadism.

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Table 1. Assessment of hypophyseal function and results of hypophyseal stimulation with an intravenous bolus of 100 µg gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH).

	First blood testing		Last blood testing	
	Time after administration of GnRH (min)		Time after administration of GnRH (min)	
	0	60	0	60
FSH (normal = 2–10 mIU/ml)	1.3	3.5	3.7	8.3
LH (normal = 1.5–10 mIU/ml)	1.6	26	6.0	43
TT (normal = 3–10 ng/ml)	0.91		5.63	
FT (normal = 8.8–27 pg/ml)	1.65		14.2	
Estradiol (normal = 11–45 pg/ml)	50		26	
Prolactin (normal = 0.5–20 ng/ml)	82.6		14.2	
Cortisol (normal = 8–25 µg/100 ml)	8.7		10.8	
ACTH (normal = 9–40 pg/ml)	20.8		21.7	
TSH (normal = 0.35–4.94 mIU/l)	1.382		1.650	
Free T4 (normal = 0.70–1.48 ng/dl)	1.03		0.99	
GH (normal = 0.06–5 ng/ml)	0.47		3.37	
IGF-1 (normal = 100–494 ng/ml)	562		266	

ACTH: Adrenocorticotrophic hormone. FSH: Follicle stimulating hormone. FT: Free testosterone. GH: Growth hormone. IGF-1: Insulin-like growth factor 1. LH: Luteinizing hormone. TSH: Thyrotropin. TT: Total testosterone.

Figure 1. Cranial MRI image showing a pituitary adenoma (White arrow).

Figure 2. Cranial MRI image showing the pituitary adenoma (White arrow) decreased in diameter.